

Spikelet sterility/grain discoloration in rice in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Spikelet sterility or grain discoloration was observed in all 24 villages that were surveyed in the West and East Godavari districts of Andhra Pradesh in the 1999 wet season. Affected varieties included MTU1001, MTU2067, MTU2077, MTU7029, BPT5204, and PLA1100. The pest problem had a patchy distribution in 23 villages and 1–21% of the rice area was affected. In one village, J.R. Gudem, 50% of the rice area was affected. The condition is referred to in the local language as “nallakanki tegulu.”

Four types of visual symptoms were observed on affected plants: mite damage alone; mite + saprophytic fungus; mite + saprophytic fungus + sheath rot fungus; and mite + white-tip nematode + other saprophytic fungal damage. After a careful examination of many samples, we concluded that the mite is the dominant organism in all cases. The mite was identified at the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI) as *Steneotarsonemus spiniki* Smiley (Tarsonemidae). *Aphelenchoides besseyi*, the white-tip nematode, was identified at the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad.

Visual symptoms such as black lesions in the leaf sheath, discolored grains, complete/partial chaffy grains, and various deformities were observed (Reissig et al 1986, Chein 1980, Rao and Prakash 1992, Rao et al 1993).

Clear mite symptoms were observed on leaves of young plants that were raised from the infested seed material, indicating that the transmission of tarsonemid mite from seed to plant is possible.

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Traditional medicinal knowledge about green leafhopper, *Nephotettix* spp., in Chhattisgarh (India)

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Green leafhoppers (GLH), principally *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stål.) and *N. virescens* (Distant), are found in all rice-growing regions of India. These species are also known pests of rice in Japan, the Philippines, Taiwan (China), and Sri Lanka. In Chhattisgarh, *Nephotettix* sp., commonly known as Hara Maho or Saunt Keda, is one of the problematic pests of rice. To farmers and agricultural scientists, GLH is a serious pest, but to folk doctors, it is a source of additional income. Native peoples of Chhattisgarh use many problematic weeds (Oudhia 1999a), insects, spiders, and mites (Oudhia 1998, 1999b) as a source of medicine.

An ethnozoological survey was conducted in Raipur, Bastar, Bilaspur, Durg, Sarguja, Mahasamund, and Rajnandgaon districts of Chhattisgarh during 1998–99 to list the medicinal uses of common and problematic pests of different agricultural crops including rice. The study focused on folk doctors older

than 60 y. In all, 20 folk doctors were interviewed and some common medicinal uses of GLH were compiled.

The survey revealed that folk doctors in the region use GLH as an additive to make traditional herbal drugs more effective. Van Bhengra (*Tridax procumbens*), a common rice weed, is used to stop any type of bleeding, and folk doctors mix fresh GLH with *Tridax* to increase its efficacy. Similarly, dried leaves of the upland weed Kukronda (*Blumea lacera*) are used to reduce the intensity of asthma attack. Dried leaves of *Blumea* with GLH are burned and the patient is advised to inhale the fumes of the mixture.

GLH was also a common major ingredient in many popular herbal combinations to treat fever and diseases such as gonorrhoea. GLH that have fed on medicinal rice var. Kalimoonch were reported to be useful for treating skin problems. Freshly crushed GLH is prepared as a paste and applied on the affected area. GLH is also popularly used as a poultry feed in the region. A folk doctor from Sarguja said that GLH and brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål.) combined can cure more than 40 diseases. The medicinal uses of GLH have not been previously reported.

This survey covered only a small number of the more than 2,000 folk doctors in Chhattisgarh practicing and using traditional systems of healing and medicine. A detailed survey is in progress and is expected to provide information on the medicinal uses of GLH and other rice pests. In this survey, folk doctors said that useful insects with high medicinal value can be easily identified through their specific behavior and feeding habits.

References

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